

Sentiment analysis became a very motivating area in both academic and industrial fields due to the exponential increase of the online published reviews and recommendations. To solve the problem of analysing and classifying those reviews and recommendations, several techniques have been proposed. Lately, deep neural networks showed promising outcomes in sentiment analysis. The growing number of Arab users on the Internet along with the increasing amount of published Arabic reviews and comments encouraged researchers to apply deep learning to analyse them. This article is a comprehensive overview of research .works that utilised the deep learning approach for Arabic sentiment analysis

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